

A REVIEW ON - CONCEPT OF DESHA**Dr. Ripsa Raj K. P.^{1*}**¹Assistant Professor Department of Swasthavritta, Atharva Ayurveda Medical College and Hospital, Dharwad, Karnataka.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Ripsa Raj K. P.**

Assistant Professor Department of Swasthavritta, Atharva Ayurveda Medical College and Hospital, Dharwad, Karnataka.

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ABSTRACT

The word "habitat" has been in use since about 1750 and derives from the Latin habitāre, to inhabit, from habēre, to have or to hold. Habitat can be defined as the natural environment of an organism, the type of place in which it is natural for it to live and grow. The chief environmental factors affecting the distribution of living organisms are intensity of light, temperature, type of soil, humidity, and climate. In Ayurveda Acharya's mentioned detailly about the Desa (land). There are mainly 3 types they are Anupa Desa (forest region /marshy land), Jangala Desa (desert land), Sadharana Desa (the land with mixed features of both Anupa and Jangala Desa). For the principles of Desa is used to Swasthya Samrakshana (for the protection of health) as well as Rogarogi Preekshana (examination of patients) itself. The main goal of Ayurveda is to create a world with healthy individuals with healthy minds and healthy surroundings. There mentioned some rituals and rejuvenations like Dinacharya (daily regimen), Ritucharya (seasonal regimen), Rasayana (rejuvenations), Sattvritta (regimen for autumn).

KEYWORDS: Desa, Tridosha, Dinacharya.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda is the one of the oldest healthcare systems that evolved in the Indian subcontinent. It is the science that evolved the well Bing of all the living beings. The maintenance of health in *Swastha* (healthy person) and treatment for diseased person is the pedestal of ayurveda. For that Acharyas explained about *Rogarogi Pareesha* (patient and disease examination) and *Swasthyasamrakshana Vidhi* (methods for protecting and maintaining health) under this one of the prime important components of *Desa*. *Desa* is again divided for accuracy of treatment and maintenance of health. *Desa* is one of the *Aturapareekshana Bhava* (tenfold examination of patient). *Prakruti* (constitution), *Sattva* (being good), *Sathmya* (conductive), *Bala* (strength), *Ojas* (life), etc. are directly and indirectly connected with *Desa*. Here mentioned about the different *Desas* and its relationship with *Tridoshas* and different landforms according to geographical view.

DHEHA DESA

Deha Desa (Humen body) or *Atura Desa* refers to the various parts of the body. That means the *Angas*

(primary body parts) and *Pratyangas* (auxiliary parts).^[7] Acharyas explained about the body parts and their features, structures, and physiology. Disease is *Nidana*(cause), *Roopas* (appearance), *Purvaroopas* (prodromes), *Samprapti* (acquisition) and *Chikitsa* (treatment) aspects are explained. *Deha Desa* is explained to examine the status of *Dosa* in the body, the life span and the *Bala* (strength) of the person.

BHUMI DESA**CLASSIFICATION OF BHUMI DESA**

In this *Bhumi Desa* is again divided into different types according to different *Achryas*. *Bhumi* is divided in to three they are *Anupa Desa* (forest region /marshy land), *Jangala Desa* (desert land), *Sadharana Desa* (the land with mixed features of both *Anupa* and *Jangala Desa*). The region which will have more features of *Anupa Desa* and less features of *Jangala* is called as *Anupa-Sadarana* (semi-forest), and that with more features of *Jangala Desa* and less of *Anupa Desa* will be *Jangala-Sadarana* (semi-desert).^[7]

Charakacharya classifies *Bhumi* into three varieties they are *Jangala Desa* (dry forest land), *Anupa Desa* (marshy land), and *Sadharana Desa* (normal land).^[1]

Other than these three kinds of *Bhumi* *Susruthacharya* classified the *Desa* as *Samanya Bhumi* (common land) and *Visesha Bhumi*. According to him the *Visesha Bhumi* is again classified into five varieties the predominance of *Panchamahabhuta* (five basic elements). They are 1) *Prthvi mahabhutaja Bhumi* (earth), 2) *Aap mahabhutaja Bhumi* (water), 3) *Agni mahabhutaja Bhumi* (fire), 4) *Vayu mahabhutaja Bhumi* (air), 5) *Akasa mahabhutaja Bhumi* (Ether).^[2]

Susruthacharya says that land endowed with *Gandha* (smell), *Varna* (color), and *Rasas* (taste) is of six types, hence combined with the nature of land, plants are endowed with six *Rasa*'s. These six *rasas* combined with the nature of land are transformed into plants. So here he gave a concept that land has also have the six *Rasa*'s which are, *Madhura* (sweet), *Amla* (sour), *Lavana* (salt), *Katu* (pungent), *Tikta* (bitter), *Kashaya* (astringent).^[3]

In *Sargadhara Samhita Poorvakhanda* Acharya mentioned herbs grown in the Vindya Mountain are *Agneya* (heat producing) while growing in Himagiri are *Sowmya* (coolant), hence a wise person should choose the suitable place before collecting. So, the quality of a herb is mostly dependent upon the place where it grows. So, the physician should collect the herbs in the *Uttharasrita* (northerly directed). The places which contain *Vatmika* (anthill), dirty place, *Anupa Desa*, *Smasana Bhoomi* (burial ground), *Usharamargaja* (salty land) are to be avoided while collecting the herbs.

Acharya *Yogaratanakara* mentioned *Trivida Desa* (three types of *Bhumis*) particularly mentioned *Matantara Desa Lakshanas*. They are *Jangala Desa*, *Anupa Desa*, *Sadharana Desa*, same opinion to *Bhavaprakasakara* also.^[9]

According to Acharya *Kasyapa* in *Khilasthana* he mentioned the 25th chapter about *Desa*. In that he mentioned about *Kurukshetra* is in under the country of hundred *Yojana*, *Purva Desa* (eastern country) and, *Dakshina Desa* (western country).^[6]

In *Raja Nighantu* Acharya explains about the *Bhumi* under *Anupadi Vargas*, in that he talked about *Trividha Bhumi* (three types of *Bhumis*), each one is classified into three types. *Anupa Desa* (Dry Forest land) and *Jangala Desa* (marshy land) are divided as 1) *Mukhya* (main), 2) *Madhyama* (moderate), and 3) *Kaniya* (ordinary), *Sadharana Desa* (normal land) divided as *Anupa Sadharana* (with more marshy characteristics) and *Jangala Sadharana* (with more dry characteristics).^[10]

Sankara are further classified on the analogy of four *Varna*'s, that is *Brahma soil* (Brahmanical character),

Ksatra soil (kshatriya character), *Vaishya soil* (Vaishya character), *Saundra soil* (Sudra character).^[10]

PREDOMINANCE OF DOSAS

Acharyas mentioned that in *Anupa Desas*, *Kapha* is predominant and causes *kaphaja Rogas*. *Jangala Desa Vata* is predominant, *Sadharana Desa* all *Thridosas* are in *Samaavastha* that is the state of equilibrium. *Susruthacharya* explains about the *Samanya Desa* which is predominant of *Kapha Dosha* and *Visishta Desa* he gave importance to *Panchamahabhutas* (five elements) and *Sadharana Desa* is predominant of *Pitta Dosa*.^[11]

PROPERTIES OF SUBSTANCES

1. **JANGALA DESA (DRY FOREST LAND):** - It abounds in open sky, it has deep forest of trees like *Kadara*, *Khadira* (*Senegaliya Catechu*), *Asasna* (*Pterocarpus marsupium*), *Aswakarna* (*Dipterocarpus turbinatus*), *Badari* (*Indian jujube*), *Tinduka* (*Diospyros mamlabarica*), *Aswatha* (*Sacred fig*), *Vada* (*Ficus benghalensis*) etc. It is mostly surrounded by trees of *Sami* (*Prosopis cineraria*), *Kakubha* (*Terminalia Juna*), and *Simsapa* (*Delbergia sissoo*) in large number. The tender branches of these trees dance, being swayed by the force of continuous dry wind. It bounds in thin, dry and rough sand as well as gravels which give rise to mirages. This area is inhabited by *Lava* (*Common quail*), *Tittiri* (*Francolin*) and *Cakora* (*Chukar*) and the people inhabiting this type of land are mostly sturdy and hardy. In *Rajanighandu* the land is divided into three which have properties like 1) *Mukhya* (main): Numerous flowing streams and marshy land. 2) *Madhyama* (moderate): water is comparatively less and thick, shadows are pierced by light. 3) *Kaniya* (ordinary): land where water is not so frequent.

2. **Anupa Desa (Marshy land):** - It contains deep forests of trees like *Hintala* (*Phoenix Paludosa*), *Tamala* (*Cinnamomum Tamala*), *Narikela* (*Coconut*) and *Kadali* (*Musa paradisiaca*). It is located generally at the banks of rivers and sea. Mostly cold wind blows here. This type of land is about rivers *Kadamba* (*Burflower tree*), *Satapatra* (*Alstinica Scholaris*) etc. and people inhabiting this type of land are tender bodies.

According to *Rajanighandu* it is fertile for *Mudga* (green gram), or leguminous grains and rice and barley type grains. This divided as 1) *Mukhya* (main): Numerous flowing streams and marshy land. 2) *Madhyama* (moderate): the land with scanty vegetations and trees. 3) *Kaniya* (ordinary): where one gets water easily by digging a well.

3. **Sadharana Desa (normal land):**- It has creepers, *Vanaspathy* (trees having fruits without apparent flowers), *Vaanaspithys* (trees having both roots and flowers) birds and beasts described above in respect

of *Jangala Desa* and *Anupa Desa* and persons inhabiting this land are sturdy, tender endowed with strength, complexion and compactness as well as other attributes of people inhabiting in the land of general nature. *Godhuma* (wheat), *Yava* (barley), *Ulbanda* (maize) usual crops grow in abundance. An ideal *Sadharana Desa* or mixed land is not possible due to inequalities in the distribution of dry and wetlands. So, the two types of *Sadharana Desa* are considered according to the availability of the difference in their characteristics.

- 4 ***Samanya Desa***: - which is free from ditches, gravels, Asma, unevenness, ant hills, and sand and not be attached to cremation ground, killing place and temple, not unfertile, fragile and with distant water sources, smooth, sprout, soft, firm, even black fair and red in color. Even growing there in the plants to be collected should be unaffected by insect's poison, weapon, sun, wind, fire, water, oppression and thorough with excellent *Rasas*, having flout and deep rooted and situated in northern quarter.
- 5 ***Visishta Desa***: - According to *Panchamahabhuta* (five basic elements) predominately describe nature.
 - i) *Prithvi mahabhutaja Desa*: which is stony, firm, heavy, blackish or black has big trees and vegetables. Alleviate diseases and enhance vitality, *Swadurasa* (sweet) predominant.
 - ii) *Aap mahabhutaja Desa*: which is smooth, cold, white with adjacent water and marsh smooth crops, grasses, and delicate trees. *Dravya*'s (plants) are *Katu* (pungent), *Kashaya* (astringent) and cool in nature.
 - iii) *Agni mahabhutaja Desa*: which are various colors, light, stony, with sparse, few pale trees and sprouts. The plants are *Tikta* (bitter), *Lavana* (salt) in taste and *Ushna* (hot) in nature. They increase appetite and remove aversion to food.
 - iv) *Vayu mahabhutaja Desa*: which is rough in color like ash and ass and has mostly small trees and those with scanty sap and cavities. *Dravyas* (plants) are *Seeta* (cold) and *Ushna* (hot), *Amla* (acidic) or feeble in nature.
 - v) *Akasa mahabhutaja Desa*: which is soft, even with ditches, water with unmanifested taste, has all around trees without pitch and big mountains and trees. *Dravya* (plants) devoid of any *Rasas* (taste).
- 6 ***Kurusketra Bhumi***: It is under the country of 100 Yojana. These living in nature of country often eat all six *Rasas*, they are brave in *Bhaksya* (the food to be masticated), *Bhojana* (to be eaten with enjoyment without mastication), cereals and eat not only once.
- 7 ***Purva Desa (eastern country)***: They are known as sweet, cold, and heavy. These are first *Kumaravartani*, then *Kalivarasa* in Magada, the Maharashtra and Rasabhadvipa, Paundravardhanaka

and *Mrittika*, *Vardhamanaka*, *karavata*, *Matanga*, *Tamralipta*, *Ciraka*, *Priyangu*, *Kausalya*, *Kalinga* and *Prasthapuraka*. The morals are seized with *Pleeha* (*Spleen*) and *Galaganda* (*Goiter*) often use jagghery, cooked *Sali* rice and fix in diet; diet is often sweet, and human beings are of *Vata* and *Sleshma* (*mucus*) in nature. For them *Katu* (*Pungenttaste*), *Tiktha* (*Bitter taste*), *Ruksha* (*Dry*), and *Ushna* (*Hot*) are the fit diet and others also which are eradivative of *Kapha* (*Muscus*) the same should be used in them.

- 8 ***Dakshina Desa (western country)***: The *Dakshina* located places are *Kancipada*, *Navadhvana*, *Kavira*, *Varanasi*, *Kumudarajya*, *Ciripali*, *Cirarajya*, of *thieves*, *Pulinda*, *Dravida*, etc.
- 9 ***Brahma Bhumi (Brahmanical character)***: The *Brahma* soil is described by *Siva*, the *Ashtamurti* having good vegetation rich in trees and enough water. The sacred grass *Kusa* (*Poa cymarosides* *Retz*) grows here abundantly. It is pleasing or delightful with white earth.
- 10 ***Ksatra Bhumi (Kshatriya character)***: The *kshatriya* soil, as described by *Pinaka* the soil consists of copper colored earth and devoid of animals. It is inaccessible due to excessive growth of *Khadira* (*Acacia Catechu*) and other thorny shrubs producing awful shrilly sounds by air passing through these shrubs.
- 11 ***Vaishya Bhumi (Vaishya character)***: The soil shining like gold with similar coloured dust, inhabited by accomplished men (*siddhas* and *kinnaras*) and full of wealth is called the soil pertaining to *Vaisyas* or business community as per description of *Indusekhar* or *Siva*.
- 12 ***Saudra Bhumi (Sudra character)***: The soil contains black coloured earth. The different varieties of grasses grow here profusely, giving immense pleasure to the growers. It is full of grass and trees like *Babool* (*Acacia Arabica*) as described by *Vrsadhway* or *Siva*.

LANDFORMS

A landform is a natural feature of the solid surface of the Earth or other planetary bodies. Landforms together make up a given terrain, and their arrangement in the landscape is known as topography.^[8]

They are categorized by characteristic physical attributes such as elevation, slope, orientation, stratification, rock exposure, and soil type. Gross physical features or landforms include intuitive elements such as *berns*, *mounts*, *hills*, *ridges*, *cliffs*, *valleys*, *rivers*, *peninsulas*, *volcanoes*, and numerous other structural and size-scaled (i.e. ponds vs. lakes, *Hills*'s. *mountains*) elements including various kinds of inland and oceanic waterbodies and sub-surface features.

CLASSIFICATION OF LANDFORMS

1) DUNES: - Dunes the most common and intriguing features of desert environment and aeolian landforms (e.g. the Cerro Blanco in Secure desert, Peru). They are mounds or small hills made up of sand, which are created due to the action of wind (or aeolian processes) and water flow under water dunes.^[11]

2) LOESS: - Loess is a deposition of silt with a little amount of sand and clay. The word 'loess' is German in origin, indicating sediments that are 'loose' in nature. It appears yellowish or brownish in color and its thickness varies from few centimeters to about 100 meters. The Missouri River of USA shows one of the thickest deposits of loess.^[12]

3) MUSHROOM ROCKS: - When a rock is subjected to intense erosion, that is non-uniform, and weathering in an arid environment, it undergoes deformation and takes the shape of what looks like a mushroom, hence the name 'mushroom rock'. Also known as 'pedestal rocks', they are, at times, formed by earthquake or external factors that cause disturbances.^[13]

4) MESA: - The word 'Mesa' has Spanish origin meaning 'table'. Mesas are also known as table mountains, owing to their distinctive appearances. These are elevated lands like mountains, characterized by presence of a flat top and steep rocks on the sides and can be mistaken for a plateau. Mesas are frequently noticed in areas that show arid to semi-arid climatic conditions.^[14]

5) BUTTE: - A 'butte' is almost like mesa and is a flat-topped hill with steep sides but covers a less amount of area than the latter. If the over-lying rock is a non-resistant one, it gives in to the wind erosion and erodes away, giving rise to the present structure. The word is originated from French word which means a Knoll.^[15]

6) CANYONS: - Canyons are like valleys, except that they are deep-seated, narrow and surrounded by steep sides. These landforms are created by erosion and by activities of rivers, winds, and glaciers. They are not a result of tectonic activities or natural disasters but are formed slowly over a long period of geological time.^[16]

7) VALLEYS: - Valleys are low-lying areas of land, situated between the hills or mountains (e.g. the California Central Valley). In most instances, they are formed by the actions of rivers and glaciers. Depending upon the shape, valley forms are classified as U-shaped, V-shaped valley and a flat-based valley.^[17]

8) HILLS: - Hills are raised portions of lands, characterized by presence of slopes (e.g. the Black Hills). They are formed due to activities of glaciers and water currents having an elevation of about 1500 ft. Different terminologies are often used to describe a hill such as mound or butte and the like. Mounds are 10 m in height,

and in simple terms are hills which are made by people.^[18]

9) PLAINS: - Plains are flat and broad land areas on the earth's surface (e.g. prairies, steppes, great plains of the Central United States). The elevation of these landforms is relatively low, when measured with reference to the mean sea level. Plains are formed due to sedimentation of the eroded soil from the hills and mountains, or due to the flowing lava deposited by the agents of wind, water, and ice.^[19]

10) PLATEAUS: - Plateaus or tablelands are large, highland flat areas, which are separated from the surrounding areas by a steep slope. The Tibetan Plateau, also referred to as 'the Roof of the World', is at an elevation of 16,000 feet. Plateaus are formed due to various actions such as collision of the earth's tectonic plates and uplift of the earth's crust by the action of magma. Also, some of the tablelands have resulted due to lava flow from the volcanic eruption.^[20]

DISCUSSION ON DINACHARYA AND DESA

In the contest of *Dinacharya* Acharya's mentions about the different Kind of Drug which is used for *Danatahdavana* (*Brushing of teeth*). Charakacharya mentioned the drugs which are used for *Dndadhavana* in Sutrasthana they are *Karanja* (*Pongamia pinnata*), *Karavira* (*Nerium indicum*), *Malati* (*Aganosma dichotoma* K Schum.), *Arka* (*Calotropis gigantea*), *Kakuba* (*Terminalia Arjuna*) and *Asana* (*Terminalia Tomentosa*).^[21] In *Kalpasthanana* in the contest of *Madanakalpa* he mentioned that the drugs like *Asana Pterocarpus marsupium*), *Kakuba*, *Khadira* will grow in the *Jangala Desa* and should be collected from there only.^[1] These drugs are predominant in *Kashaya* (*Astringent*), *Katu* (*Pungent*) and *Tiktarasa* (*Bitter*) and *Jangala Desa* is Predominant in *Vatapitta*. *Triphala*, *Trikatu* and *Trijatata* are mentioned for *Danthagharshana* (*Dental friction*). In that *Amalki* (*Indian gooseberry*) collected from *Jangaladesa*.

CONCLUSION

Desas are important to maintain health and identify diseases. For the treatment of disease one who adopted *Ahara* (food) and *Oushadi* (*medicine*) in the land mentioned by Acharyas. These have the properties of that *Desa*, and which will subside the *Doshas* and nourish *Dhatus* in proper manner. In Ayurveda and geography have mentioned specific details about the *Desa* or landforms with respect to the living organisms. So, in general we can assume and predict that *Desa* or the landforms help the preservation of health and longevity.

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